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THE SCHOOL COUNCIL IN AN EDUCATIONAL, DEMOCRATIC, AND PARTICIPATORY ENVIRONMENT: RESHAPING THE PARADIGM OF EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this article is to analyze the role and functionality of the School Council in an educational, democratic, and participatory environment, from the perspective of 21st-century educational paradigms. Thus, it demonstrates the differences between councils, their importance, and their functionality in contributing to the educational process at the Luiz Pereira Junior High School of Reference (EREM) in the municipality of Caetés (PE), within the sphere in which the school is situated for the exercise of its activities, as indicated by the concepts of Democratic and Participatory Management, where a Democratic State of Law is affirmed. From this, the analysis developed through a comparison of data with the perspectives of authors, legislation, and conceptions about Education Councils and Schools. There are still factors, misconceptions, and conceptual gaps that prevent the effective implementation of democratic and participatory management within Education Councils and School Councils. This includes identifying that certain priority segments lack social value due to political and personal interference from municipal/state administrations, directly resulting in a lack of transparency to society and the community in which the school is located, thus creating constant and unsolvable paradigms. It is recommended to seek the effective legitimacy of democratic and participatory management in public schools, bringing to the forefront of discussions a direct selection process for the school administrator position by the school community, as well as the inclusion of parent and/or guardian representatives in this position to proportionally validate the democratic process.

Keywords: School Council. Education. Legislation

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary times, it is understood that the positions needed to consolidate the technique and/or methods for monitoring the performance and/or practice of teaching; the applicability of the curriculum and the very evolution of the students are not solely the role of a single element. The conception and concepts that a collegiate body can contribute to promoting the consolidation of current educational legislation, as well as the applicability of related actions, contemplating the necessary transparency in the effective use of material and financial resources for the benefit of school and educational activities, are being built.

In this context, even if there is a mitigation, and in many cases the elimination of existing problems in the school and educational environment in the three academic spheres: municipal, state and federal, the proposal to implement the School Council as a participatory and/or democratic management tool can shape many positive perspectives on this subject. (PARO, 2007).

From this perspective, and grounded in concepts from other global education frameworks, there are directions for consolidating equal education for all, also promoting the importance of societal participation in actions, as a body overseeing the development and application of the resources involved. Therefore, the need arises for a specific body that should hypothetically be constituted to contribute to the application of current legislation, as well as having the autonomy to oversee resources for educational and school purposes. This prompts many discussions about aspects still in constant conflict with the understanding of its freedom of action, and what the correct direction is for establishing a body that is independent of political issues and contradictory to the understanding of the democratic process existing in Brazilian territory after the 1988 Federal Constitution.

Currently, the hierarchical existence of the following basic "Councils" in education can be highlighted: National Education Council (CNE); State Education Council (CEE); Municipal Education Council (CME); and the School Council (exclusive to each public and/or private educational institution).

With the exception of the National Education Council and the School Council, all have representatives from segments of Civil Society, formed by pairs, that is, for example, if there are three governmental representatives, there must necessarily be three non-governmental representatives (e.g., institutions and/or bodies that represent the community: Neighborhood Associations; Philanthropic Associations that are not financed by the Public Power). However, there are only Parent representatives who are totally independent, as they are the ones who directly represent the students enrolled in the schools.

Therefore, for this reason, the concern is to choose as the object of study the analysis of the role and functionality of the School Council in the educational, democratic, and participatory environment, from the perspective of the paradigms of 21st-century education at the Luiz Pereira Junior High School of Reference (EREM Luiz Pereira Junior). In this sense, the article aims to advance a discussion of how this impacts the School Community, requiring, first of all, consideration of the historical moment in which it is situated; and of the references used for the development of the School Council.

METHODOLOGY

Research consists of a formal process for obtaining knowledge about a given reality, requiring reflection and scientific rigor. Although it seeks the truth, it is not limited to it. Therefore, the objective of scientific research is to seek, in an in-depth manner, answers to all the questions that are part of the investigation. According to Medeiros (2014), for these reasons, the investigative process that involves all research "[...] uses scientific methods, systematic reflection, control of variables, careful observation of facts, establishment of laws or checking of information with already acquired knowledge" (MEDEIROS, 2014, p. 38).

In this sense, important aspects were observed that need to be fulfilled to compose the evidence of the importance of the Councils for the School Community.

With the tabulation of bibliographic data, we sought

to add relevant concepts and perspectives adopted by the research subjects regarding the elaboration and development of the Council's activities for the school and the students.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESEARCH

For the development of the research, two questionnaires were applied: the conceptual investigation questionnaire, which broadly identified the behaviors and conceptions about the Council that the interviewees possess, and the interview, which obtained answers to the objectives pre-established in the construction of the Research Project for the implementation of this work.

It is important to highlight that this process was carried out from the perspective of constructing the necessary analyses to achieve the objectives listed in the introductory chapter, which presents the specific objectives of this work.

The operation of a School Council in the educational context in a school in the interior of Pernambuco was very significant in demonstrating the importance and, above all, the need for the re-signification of the concept and behaviors existing in this institution.

The development of the study was based on the investigation of the operational and ideological processes of the School Council in a state-run public school in the municipality of Caetés (PE).

Thus, data collection will follow the structural aspects below:

Table 1 - Objectives for research participants

Role	Instruments			Objective
	TCLE	Questionnaire (1)	Interview (2)	
Manager	Yes	Yes	Yes	To discuss knowledge of the historicity and participation in democratic management within the School Council
Teachers	Yes	Yes	Yes	To examine knowledge about the role and functionality of the School Council
Parents and/or guardians	Yes	Yes	Yes	To ascertain the knowledge and participation of agents in the functionality of the School Council

Source: Author's data, 2022.

However, there are situations where the use of a closed and standardized instrument, such as a standardized questionnaire, is necessary and advantageous, ensuring, according to Laville and Dionne (2008), a unified perspective on the questions, their order, and choices, whether they concern knowledge, beliefs, feelings, values, interests, expectations, aspirations, fears, and behaviors, facilitating the gathering and comparison of chosen responses, as well as accepting the use of statistical tools during analysis. The choice to apply a standardized questionnaire in this investigation consists of translating the collected data objectively and reliably into "the objects of the research into specific questions" (GIL, 2010, p. 121).

The initial proposal of this study aimed to demonstrate the importance of the work and development of democratic activities within the school environment. In this field, it was observed that the performance and applicability of theories aimed at the prosperity of democratic concepts are still linked to counter-arguments related to the unilateral idealism of a cultural domain still in force in Brazilian education.

This issue is perceived, mainly, because within the educational sphere there is still a hierarchical and political "power" related to the presentation of educational and social public policies that still point to the State's dominance in the construction of citizenship and socio-culturalism geared towards a proposal, as highlighted in Freire's (1980) construction of knowledge, a dominance of dominant forces in an education that claims to be autonomous, but even in contemporary times old customs and practices are enshrined where the student and their family must serve what society expects from their evolution in their social groups.

Also discussed is the existing misunderstanding between the School Council and the Executive Unit, namely:

It is essential not to confuse School Council with Executive Unit. The School Council is a collegiate body within the school structure, composed of the principal and representatives of teachers, other staff, parents or guardians, students, and the local community (if applicable), whose role is to decide on pedagogical, administrative, and financial matters within the school. In contrast, an Executive Unit is a

private, non-profit entity representing public schools, comprised of members of the school community responsible for formalizing the procedures necessary for receiving the transfer of financial resources allocated to schools, as well as for the execution and accountability of these resources. (BRAZIL. 2020, p. 10).

The process of redefining the Councils is still a struggle that will be independent of municipal managers. Amidst the achievements, what can be observed is that the representation of parents and/or guardians is still at the mercy of partisan politics and inconsistencies developed by people who lack honesty in their actions, and who would be very beneficial to the society in which the school is located.

The literature on the issue of financial resources that contribute to the work of the Councils is still scarce; however, it is worth looking into improving this topic, demonstrating that the existing gaps in the Councils due to a lack of members and their respective representatives are a manifestation imposed by those who do not accept or do not want democratic and participatory work within the school.

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Starting from this ideological and especially philosophical construction, it should be noted that the work to build an autonomous Council is still an invisible struggle in the eyes of Brazilian society, and especially schools, aiming at preventing the growth of a society that is still in a vulnerable situation.

Having as sociocultural principles the necessary objectivity to change the political and doctrinal aspects that, even in contemporary times, make the formation of a Council an internal conduct to enable actions related to public policies that give financial rights to educational institutions, from Elementary School to the final stage of High School (e.g., School

Transportation), it is necessary to build new paths to be followed and conducted with a true practice of democratic management.

A conduct seen in articles, conceptions and formations of concepts about the practice of democratic management points to the development of actions among school managers, however, it must be expressed that in Brazil, the identification of a democratic management that involves the possible work of parents and/or guardians of students in school management is still very low.

The main situations that are being made possible through public education policies demonstrate that there is still a long way to go for education scholars, as well as for the "managers" who, in some cases, act as puppets for the development of the Councils, as well as to hinder educational progress in their region.

As a positive perspective for the development of democratic and, above all, participatory management, adopt a practice relating all subjects declared and made effective as members of the school community to the list of candidates for filling an existing vacancy in the School Councils. To occupy the role of president of this body, one must discuss in a way that understands and makes effective all the rationality and, above all, objectivity existing in the current legislation, starting initially with changing the understanding that a School Council can be chaired by a parent as long as there are pre-established requirements in accordance with the functions discussed in the specific legislation for the formation and operation of the School Council.

The legislation for the Fundeb Social Support and Control Councils and the School Food Council already allows for the appointment of parent representatives as presidents, although gaps are still found in the performance of the functions and practices carried out by them.

Another point, still questionable and which represents a confrontation even for the understanding of democratic and participatory management, is the appointment of parent and/or guardian representatives in the management of public schools, something that

is expressed and understood by current legislation that these representatives do not have the competence for such functions.

Many issues were observed and identified during the research, demonstrating that there are numerous situations in which the presented democratic and participatory management. This violates conceptions, discernments and theories of the formation of the process. It then leads to the understanding that there is still no organization, or even a proposal, that leads education managers and a politically active society to follow the innovative and victorious path of democracy through the participation of all.

In Brazil, the theme of democratic and participatory school management still faces many perspectives that are not related to the essence of democratic and participatory concepts. Although there are many discourses about school management being an almost necessary and enriching action and behavior for the benefit of public schools, many discrepancies and stumbles are identified, as well as questions that are not answered by educational theorists and philosophers in a concrete way, resorting to negative conceptions that are not considerably accepted by a large part of society and the school community.

When answered, the discernments and statements are impositions that go against the theories and conceptions of democracy, leaving aside many reasons that do not list an innovative proposal for change.

Romão Netto (2015), in his work on "new public management," characterized the important participation of parents in the management of public education institutions, mainly based on the neoliberal thinking of President Fernando Henrique Cardoso, who always presented as the main goal of his government the adoption of an administration carried out and made effective with the participation of all, since popular participation is one of the conditions for the realization of democracy. In this sense, problems arose that, over time, became obstacles fostered by negative and non-liberating perspectives on democracy.

Other important aspects, such as the foundations for the development of a "new public management," were in the thinking and what was strongly opposed by organizations, mainly educational ones, through their public managers, the administrative reform presented by Bresser-Pereira (2009). (ROMÃO NETTO, 2015). The administrative reform, which should present resources and means of social, cultural, and administrative inclusion within state ownership, since this could be a tool against still elitist positions that believe, even in contemporary times, to dominate Brazilian education, or any public body of interest to the less favored society.

CONCLUSION

The development of this work made it possible to form, as well as design, important reflections on the role of educational institutions, as well as the ideology necessary for the growth of the behaviors of School Councils and Education Councils in the face of the thinking of democratic and participatory management.

The study also demonstrated that, given the perspectives of the subjects who participated in the field research, it was understood that they are not sufficiently able to be autonomous in the discussion of the themes that open up, from the relevance of the role of the council and its councilors to the actions that can lead and transform into partnerships the goals for educational enrichment in a public school.

This study also identified that one of the biggest negative manifestations for the non-recognition of Education and School Councils is the participation, contrary to legal norms and beneficial to society, of municipal managers, who in the vast majority of cases have the collaboration of educational managers.

In this sense, the objective of this article was to analyze the role and functionality of the school council in the educational, democratic, and participatory environment, which led to the understanding that the formation of a school community requires more in-depth studies on the behavior and practice of including concepts about the relevance of councils in a public school, since the democratic and participatory process in an

educational institution is still intertwined with perspectives of discrediting these bodies.

The behavioral aspects of democratic management still open up a range of information about the conduct and the way it is developed not only in the school field of research, but in a general way, where the mismatch between the concept of participation of the research subjects and the effectiveness of democratic acts for the benefit of the school and the community in which it is located is found.

Initially, the importance of the school council in a democratic and participatory environment becomes clear. It was identified in all conceptual and philosophical contexts that the work, being coherent and developed without any political and/or partisan interference, reaffirms the functionality of the School Council as a positive path for the development of democratic and participatory behaviors of those who act and participate actively, from management to the participatory role of parents in the school (for example, the school cleaning work parties).

The path still to be traveled for the formation of concepts and conceptions that would not vulgarize the councils requires more practices and acceptance from educational and school managers.

There are many criteria that need to be changed in the legislation governing Education and School Councils, including actions that can revolutionize the manipulative behavior of managers who do not aim for the evolution of education. These could act innovatively within the parameters of existing democratic concepts in Brazil, as well as in a participatory manner. Therefore, it is understood that changes are necessary in view of the effective participation of parents and/or guardians in the management of public schools. This leads to the composition of a range of criteria so that this can be carried out productively and insightfully within the legal parameters of Brazilian educational legislation.

Thus, what can be concluded from the development of this study is the incoherence of the understanding of democratic management, with regard to participatory actions, as well as the inconsistencies in the formation

of school and education councils, and also the low vision of teachers who believe that the councils are a tool that has a supervisory and deliberative character only in favor of the municipal or state manager.

It is believed that in the not-too-distant future, Education and School Councils will be more autonomous, and with their own resources, they will be able to be redefined in a way that reflects the Brazilian reality, thus ensuring the participation of all and guaranteeing the implementation of acts of democratic and participatory management within the society in which the school is embedded.

REFERENCES

BRASIL. Conselho de Acompanhamento e Controle Social do FUNDEB. Available at < https://www.fnde.gov.br/fnde_sistemas/cacs-fundeb >. Accessed at Oct. 10, 2020.

BRASIL. Conselhos escolares. [artigo] Ministério da Educação, 2018. Available at <<http://portal.mec.gov.br/programa-nacional-de-fortalecimento-dos-conselhos-escolares>>. Accessed at Apr. 20, 2020

BRASIL. Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil: promulgada em 5 de outubro de 1988. Available at: <http://www.planalto.gov.br>. Accessed at Mar. 29, 2018.

BRASIL. Lei 9394/96: Lei de Diretrizes e Bases da Educação Nacional.

Available at www.casacivil.gov.br. Accessed at Feb. 20, 2016.

BRASIL. Curso de Formação para Conselheiros Escolares: Módulo 1 – Conselho Escolar na democratização da escola. UFG, 2020. Available at < <http://www.labtime.ufg.br/modulos/conselheiros-escolares/uni1/slide1.html> >. Accessed at May. 30, 2022.

BRASIL. Resolução N° 26, de 17 de junho de 2013. Dispõe sobre o atendimento da alimentação escolar aos alunos da educação básica no âmbito do

Programa Nacional de Alimentação Escolar PNAE: Fundo Nacional de Desenvolvimento da Educação. Available at < <http://www.fn-de.gov.br/aceso-a-informacao/institucional/legislacao/item/4620-resolu%C3%A7%C3%A3o-cd-fnde-n%C2%BA-26,-de-17-de-junho-de-2013> > Accessed at Jun. 23, 2018.

BRASIL. Lei Nº 13.502, de 1º de novembro de 2017. Estabelece a organização básica dos órgãos da Presidência da República e dos Ministérios; altera a Lei no 13.334, de 13 de setembro de 2016; e revoga a Lei no 10.683, de 28 de maio de 2003, e a Medida Provisória no 768, de 2 de fevereiro de 2017. Available at <http://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2015-2018/2017/lei/L13502.htm> Accessed at Jun 23, 2018.

BRASIL. Escola de Gestores da Educação Básica: Apresentação. Brasília: Ministério da Educação, 2022. Available at < <http://portal.mec.gov.br/escola-de-gestores-da-educacao-basica>>. Accessed at May. 30, 2022.

CONSELHO DE ALIMENTAÇÃO ESCOLAR. ATA n. 10 – Reunião Extraordinário para alterações da Lei do Conselho. Garanhuns. 13 ago. 2018.

FREIRE, Paulo. Pedagogia do oprimido. Rio de Janeiro: Paz e Terra, 1983.

FREIRE, Paulo. Pedagogia da autonomia: saberes necessários à prática educativa. São Paulo: Paz e Terra, 1996

GIL, Antonio Carlos. Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa. 5. ed. São Paulo: Atlas, 2010.

LAVILLE, Christian; DIONNE, Jean. A construção do saber: manual de metodologia da pesquisa em ciências humanas. Porto Alegre: Artmed; Belo Horizonte: Editora UFMG, 1999.

MEDEIROS, João Bosco. Redação científica: a prática de fichamentos, resumos, resenhas. 12. ed.

São Paulo: Atlas, 2014.

PARO, V. H. Estrutura da escola e prática educacional democrática. GT: Estado e Política Educacional / n.05-Agência Financiadora: CNPq. Caxambu – MG, out. / 2007. Available at < <http://30reuniao.anped.org.br/trabalhos/GT05-2780--Int.pdf> >. Accessed at May. 20, 2020.

PARO, V. H. Gestão Democrática da Escola Pública. 3.ed. São Paulo, Ática, 2005.

ROMÃO NETTO, J. V. Gestão de políticas de cultura e qualidade da democracia: São Paulo, 10 anos de um modelo ainda em construção. Revista Administração Pública. Rio de Janeiro v.49, n. 4, p.: 1011-1037, jul./ ago., 2015. Available at <<https://www.scielo.br/j/rap/a/pPXzHvrfkxHsfG4n9p97Kq/?format=pdf&lang=pt>> Accessed at Jan. 20, 2022.